

PERCEPTION OF NIGERIAN MILITARY PERSONNEL ON INTER-AGENCY COOPERATION AND PEACE SUPPORT OPERATIONS OF THE NIGERIAN ARMED FORCES

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Abstract: Conflicts may be managed and insecurity contained via synergy and cooperation. Due to the various security agencies' diverse capabilities and operational expertise, they can complement each other. Given the responsibilities of various security agencies, it's fair to say that violent conflict in communities will be reduced to a minimum if these constitutional functions are well-played in conjunction with one another as intended by society. The objectives of the study include: the examination of Nigerian Armed Forces benefits from interagency cooperation; an analysis of the nature of the relationship between the various agencies involved in peace support operations; and an examination of the challenges faced by Nigerian Armed Forces personnel during peace support operations with other agencies. The survey was conducted by administering a questionnaire to 88 military personnel through Google Forms to observe the COVID-19 safety protocol. The modified five-point Likert-types rating scale was used for the questionnaire and data analysis, which shows a statistically significant large positive correlation between the two variables as $r = .936$, $p < 0.05$. This indicates that peace support operation has a close relationship with inter-agency cooperation where the experienced and expertise of individuals collaboration, the more satisfied they are with their missions. It was concluded that soldiers, especially those from developing countries such as Nigeria, stand to benefit from participating in peace support operations with the following recommendation that a result of the findings suggest that the Nigerian government and military take a closer look at the administrative and logistical assistance they provide for troops deployed to PSOs to correct the shortcomings.

Keywords: Perception, Nigerian Military Personnel, Inter-Agency Cooperation, Peace Support Operations and the Nigerian Armed Forces.

1. INTRODUCTION

National security architecture of a country includes security management, decision-making processes, oversight structures and security institutions. It also involves national policies, strategies and plans on security. Several institutions and agencies in a coordinating mode contribute to national security management, as this impacts on coordinated decision-making which is important in a nation (Bearne et al., 2015). Peacekeeping missions in the modern era face a wide range of challenges. In the United Nations' view, peacekeeping is a method of ensuring that peace is maintained, no matter how tenuous, in areas where fighting has been halted. While peacekeeping has traditionally relied on military forces to enforce cease-fires and separate forces after interstate conflicts, it has evolved into a more complex model that includes civilians and security agencies working together to lay the groundwork for a feeling of lasting peace. We need continued support for Nigeria, which has taken on an ever-increasing share of the peacekeeping burden in Western Africa since the early '90s. Nigeria is

currently the largest African contributor to UN peacekeeping operations and the UN's fourth-largest financial contributor worldwide.

Psychology has provided more understanding into adverse deviant behaviour (such as psychiatric illness) than good deviants (such as inventiveness) in the current state of humanity (Galtung, 2011). Even though it's common knowledge that peace is defined as "non-war," it's unfortunate that studies focus on conflicts rather than periods of peace. As long as there's no war, peace isn't at its highest height. When it comes to defining peace as the elimination of conflict, the dilemma of how to conceptualise war as the dearth of peace arises. "This manner of conceptualising peace, albeit seductive, is inadequate for comprehending the nature of peace," he says.

Many well-known peace scholars Boulding (2011); Galtung (2015); Vasquez (2015) agree that peace is not the absence of war but institutional mechanisms for nonviolent conflict management. Isn't it obvious? Long-standing commercial tensions have not escalated into armed confrontations between the United States of America and the European Union (EU), instead of being resolved diplomatically through the World Trade Organization (WTO) (WTO). A state's primary responsibility in fostering and promoting global progress is to ensure the safety of its citizens. In a democratic society, there are numerous ways to ensure that peace is maintained. However, the methods to be used are determined by understanding long-term viability and the available resources (finances and personnel). Regardless of a country's approach, security agencies must work together (Boulding, 2011; Galtung, 2015; Vasquez, 2015).

Conflicts can be managed and insecurity contained through synergy and cooperation. Due to the unique capabilities and operational skills of the various security agencies, they can complement each other. James (2010) and Ahmed (2017) have identified the three broad elements of Nigeria's national and internal security as the secret intelligence agencies, the military component (armed forces), and the law enforcement agencies. Gbanite (2011) also advocated for inter-agency cooperation in dealing with internal security issues (2011). To strengthen all of the country's security agencies, he argues that Nigeria needs the commitment of security personnel and financial mobilisation. According to Gbanite (2011), this country's safety depends on the National Security Agency (NSA) having specific, measurable goals.

Objectives set forth by the National Security Agency (NSA) must be communicated to all of the agencies that make up Nigeria's police force, national intelligence agency, immigration service, state security service, NDLEA, Ministry of Interior, and Nigeria Customs Service (NCS). It is the job of the Defense Intelligence Agency (DIA) to coordinate all of the military intelligence agencies (DMI, DNIA, and DAF) into a single, cohesive effort (DAI). A threat to Nigeria's security could come from the outside or within, depending on the information gathered; to get to the proper agency authorised to put down an insurgency, this information should be shared with the NSA. From the above, it is clear that each of the components of Nigeria's security organisations plays a distinct but complementary role. There are clearly distinct roles and tasks for all agencies, according to Ajayi (2015). Collaboration in Nigeria is unhealthy due to the failure of one agency to carry out its responsibilities effectively. Revitalisation or reform should be the choice here. A government agency may be willing to carry out its duties effectively, as a result of prohibitive small budgetary allocation, it will not achieve its full potential. To say that if the roles of the various security agencies are well played in cooperation with one another as envisaged by the society, there will be minimal violence in our community would be correct (Odoma, 2011). While the need for inter-agency cooperation grows, the distrust and lack of cooperation among agencies appear to have remained constant. The highest levels of the military seem to be alarmed, but institutional obstacles appear to be beyond their capabilities (Nigerian Tribune, 2013).

The United Nations Charter serves as the global standard for all Peace Support Operations (PSOs). According to the UN Charter's first article, the UN's mission is to maintain global peace and security and to accomplish this. The UN works to implement effective collective procedures for deterring and eradicating threats to peace, eradicating acts of aggression and other cracks in the peace and facilitating peaceful means of resolving global disputes or situations that could lead to war. UN Charter article 33, chapter VI, provides for pacific settlement of disputes between nations through negotiations, mediations and inquiries, and judicial, arbitration recourse to provincial agencies or provisions, and other peaceful means of their choice to fulfil this responsibility. While Chapter VII is primarily designed to deal with threats to peace, cracks in the peace, and acts of aggression by sovereign states, it is essentially coercive. In Chapter VIII, regional organisations are given the authority to assist in the maintenance and restoration of peace in their respective subregions. Troops-contributing nations like Nigeria have been at the forefront of supporting UN, regional, and sub-regional PSOs since the country gained independence from Britain in 1960 (Odoma, 2011).

As peace mediators and implementers, Nigerians have made a significant contribution to reducing conflict throughout the world, particularly in Africa. However, in Angola in 1993 and Rwanda in 1994, some of those accords failed to take hold. The Democratic Republic of the Congo (DRC), Cote D'Ivoire, Darfur, and Somalia's situations didn't improve, leading to large-scale internal displacement and refugee crises that have only exacerbated the already precarious security situation in and around these conflict zones. Recently, military missions have become more diverse, incorporating a wider range of non-traditional tasks than ever before. Insurgency fighting and nation-building go hand-in-hand. These responsibilities include intelligence gathering, threat assessment, tactical warfighting to peacemaking, civil affairs administration, infrastructure improvement, and the development of local security organisations (Odoma, 2011).. For the Army to be effective in this new set of missions, it must combine tactical expertise with the ability to take advantage of nonmilitary advantages, particularly by forming partnerships with local organisations and individuals. As one of the most significant troop contributors after Bangladesh and India, the Nigerian Army (NA) has taken part in UN peacekeeping missions throughout its history. The United Nations Security Council voted to include Nigeria in the Security Council because of its commitment to and contributions to the UN peace mission. The fact that Nigeria was elected to the African Union Peace and Security Council in 2004 and served as the Council's first chairman from that year onward confirms the accomplishments and leadership roles she has held since the early days of the Organizations of the African Union (OAU) (Odoma, 2011).. Military participation in peace support operations is motivated by personal reasons. The Nigerian military is not motivated financially, and the Nigerian government has abandoned their immediate family when they participate in peace operations. These issues have not been addressed. As evidenced by a cursory investigation, no empirical studies have shown how participation in peace support operations affects the Nigerian military. The body of knowledge about peacekeeping's effectiveness has grown considerably over the years. The "value-added" of peacekeeping cannot be assessed because much of the second-wave literature on the subject only looks at situations in which peacekeepers were deployed. Comprehensive statistical studies of all wars remedied this problem. One of the main drawbacks is exposing a weak peacekeeping model that the founders had assumed (Odoma, 2011)..

Peacekeeping is interested in whether or not peacekeepers tend to take on the easier cases or, the more difficult ones. To put it another way, peacekeepers cannot make much of a difference if they only go to places where peace is already established. As a result, when peacekeepers find themselves in more challenging situations, their efforts are even more impressive. A mutually advantageous and well-defined partnership entered into by two or more organisations to pursue a common purpose is what Townsend and Shelly (2018) call "inter-agency cooperation. Mutual obligations and goals, a common framework, and shared responsibilities" are part of this agreement. "According to them, the inter-agency collaboration also means sharing resources and rewards as well as establishing mutual authority and accountability for achievement.

According to Neyla et al. (2015), who looked at inter-agency cooperation in the context of US defence strategy from a military perspective, it had developed slowly, starting with the first Army-Navy Board in 1903 during the American-Spanish conflict. While some scholars believe that inter-agency collaboration is a cross-agency collaboration that recognises the record and disseminates information on related services, it also identifies gaps and overlays in services and areas of agency proficiency. It leads to planned decision making that broadens the collective capacities of contributors (Timmons et al., 2015). While outlining the numerous benefits of inter-agency collaboration, Best (2017) emphasised that it allows the parties involved to work together on their own to find solutions to problems through constructive communication and other activities like collaborative projects. Collaboration fosters mutual respect, trust, and confidence among the parties involved. Conflict parties, both potential and real, can work together on a number of recognised common topics and themes, resulting in increased communication and activity. Interpersonal, group, community, national, regional, and global interactions culminate in this interaction. People who work with one another are more likely to form close friendships and highly regard one another.

With this research, Nigeria's support for peacekeeping efforts in Africa and Nigeria will be better understood. It has helped shed light on the goals of the UN in Nigeria, making it easier to weigh the tradeoffs between the profits and drawbacks of the project.

Research Questions

The research aims to answer the following questions:

- i. How has the Nigerian Armed Forces benefited by engaging in peace support operations through interagency cooperation?

- ii. What is the nature of the relationship among the various security agencies in peace support operations?
- iii. What challenges are confronting the Nigerian Armed Forces personnel during peace support operations with other agencies?

Objectives of the Study

The study's overarching goal is to examine the perception of Nigeria military personnel on inter-agency cooperation and peace support operations. The study's precise goals are to:

- i. Examined the Nigerian Armed Forces benefits by engaging in peace support operations through interagency cooperation.
- ii. Analyse the nature of the relationship among the various security agencies in peace support operations.
- iii. Examined the challenges confronting the Nigerian Armed Forces personnel during peace support operations with other agencies.

Empirical Review

Because of its unwavering commitment to world peace, Nigeria has become well-known throughout the world community. Nigeria's World War II neutrality made her a trusted mediator and a sought-after member of peacekeeping troops in war zones (Adewuyi, 2015). The Nigerian Army took part in a large number of operations supported by the United Nations. The Economic Community of West African States (ECOWAS), the African Union (AU) were established by the OAU's order, which included some of these countries. Onourah (2013) has pointed out that Nigeria provides PSOs with troops and equipment without specifying its intentions or national interest. Despite its efforts in Liberia and Sierra Leone, the United States was unable to exert any influence in both countries. More than 150,000 Nigerian militaries have participated in 43 peace support missions, according to Onwuamaegbu (2019). The Nigerian Army had a significant impact during this period, serving as a leader in many of these missions.

In the early 1960s, shortly prior to Nigeria's independence, Nigeria served as a peacekeeper in the Democratic Republic of Congo. That operation was led by the late Nigerian Maj Gen JIU Aguiyi Ironsi, who was also a UN commander. Nigeria sent troops to Angola as part of UN Angola Verification Mission II (UNAVEM II), which was overseen by Maj Gen Chris Abutu Garba (rtd). Abutu Garba is Nigeria's top military officer. Aside from being a major troop-contributing country (TCC) to the UN missions in both Liberia and Sudan, Nigerian generals Lt Gen Owonibi and Lt Gen ML Agwai led the African Union-United Nations hybrid operation in Darfur (UNAMID). Nigerian Army involvement in PSOs around the world include:

- i. Sub-regional stability in Liberia and Sierra Leone was restored through ECOMOG.
- ii. Reducing the use of child soldiers and tiny weaponry in West Africa's sub-region by mercenary armies.
- iii. The United States launched a peacekeeping mission in Chad on its own back in 1979.
- iv. Contributed to establishing a model PSO for other regional organisations, such as the Southern African Development Community (SADC) and the Sahel-Saharan States Community (CEN-SAD).
- v. Recognition as a PSO participant around the world.

International peacekeeping missions have benefited greatly from Nigeria's efforts. Her government has spearheaded, funded, and coordinated African peace missions. Additionally, Nigeria has enthusiastically participated in various UN peace involvements around the world, making available men and women of its police force, naval, army, and air force. With the help of the Nigerian military, the African Union Mission in Sudan (AMIS) received massive backing from the country's armed forces (Human Rights Watch, 2016). The ECOMOG PSOs in Sierra Leone and Liberia crises drew in about 12,000 troops (Abdurrahman, 2015). With a total of 3,404 soldiers, Nigeria was second only to Bangladesh in terms of troop contributions to UN peacekeeping missions in the world in 2000. (Ebegbulem, 2012). The number of Nigerian soldiers supporting UN operations rose by 55 percent between 2007 and 2008 to 5,271 personnel (Okereke, 2019). By 2013, the number of Nigerian soldiers serving as UN peacekeepers in various war zones had surpassed 6,000. (Hamman & Omojuwa, 2015). Military personnel in Nigeria must fulfil these duties throughout various peacekeeping missions.

Basic empirical concerns such as whether peacekeeping makes peace more enduring and why some missions are more effective than others have been attempted in a clearer and more social scientifically rigorous approach than previous studies on the subject. The qualitative and quantitative approaches have been used to address these issues. Much of the second-

wave research on peacekeeping focuses on situations in which peacekeepers were deployed, rather than those in which they were not, making it impossible to scientifically measure the "value-added." This was a shortcoming that was remedied by comprehensive statistical studies of all battles.

Some of these quantitative studies have looked at peace support activities in their conventional interstate setting. Interstate conflict is not prevented by UN intervention, according to Diehl et al. (1996). Fortna (2013) finds that peace lasts far longer when international personnel are deployed when states are left to their own devices to maintain peace. Fewer studies specifically compare or contrast peacekeeping in civil and interstate wars. It is widely assumed that peacekeeping in civil wars is more difficult and less successful (Diehl 1993, Weiss 1998). According to a few studies, peacekeeping is at least as effective in civil conflicts in interstate ones (Heldt, 2002). Civil wars are the focus of the vast majority of quantitative research into the effects of peacekeeping (perhaps not surprisingly, as most of the current peacekeeping needs are internal conflicts). In the end, these investigations have come to an encouraging conclusion. According to Dubey (2002), certain studies have thrown doubt on the efficiency of peacekeeping in general, and several distinctions have been drawn between the effects of peacekeepers on establishing and then maintaining peace (Greig & Diehl 2015, Gilligan & Sergenti 2017).

A strong result in the quantitative literature shows that peacekeeping reduces the likelihood of civil war resuming once a truce is established. Plethora of research (Doyle & Sambanis in 2020 and by Walter & Fortna in 2014; Gilligan & Sergenti in 2017) have demonstrated a statistically significant impact of peacekeeping on time after civil wars. However, despite its limitations and failures, peacekeeping is surprisingly effective in maintaining peace. Despite the fact that peacekeepers in some places (such as Cyprus or Kosovo) have difficulty leaving because they are afraid that violence may erupt again as soon as they leave, peacekeepers have generally been very successful in ensuring long-lasting peace once their mission has ended. Namibia, Mozambique, El Salvador, Croatia, and the West African peacekeeping force in Guinea-Bissau are just a few of the examples. Numerous studies on the impact of peacekeeping on the recurrence of conflict have pointed out that the odds are stacked against peacekeeping in some way. The use of peacekeeping is not a random act; rather, it is linked to other elements that determine whether or not a state of peace will continue. This endogeneity is hard to find contributory variables to deal with endogeneity. Gilligan and Sergenti (2017) employed matching algorithms. It has been addressed statistically and qualitatively in bigger peacekeeping studies to account for any spuriousness. Fortna (2013) also engages in a comprehensive study of where peacekeepers control possible spuriousness.

Howard (2018) points out that peacekeeping has an overall favourable effect on civil war outcomes. UN peacekeeping deployments that are similar in terms of mandate implementation and domestic institutions' ability to function after the mission's departure are compared using qualitative approaches. "Organisational learning" has been found to boost an organization's ability to gather and share knowledge as well as engage with the local populace. It is also essential to have a field-based peacekeeping operation in place because that represents another pillar of success. Quantitative and qualitative methods are used by Fortna (2013) to evaluate whether peacekeeping has an effect and how it affects, i.e., the causal mechanisms of peacekeeping, respectively.

Problems Militating Against Inter-Agency Cooperation in Peace Support Operations in Nigeria. There is a wide range of circumstances in which interagency cooperation is likely to be deemed essential. Unrest among students, community conflicts and religious conflicts, accidents, and natural calamities are among the examples given by Shiyabade (2000). Insurgency, political/electoral violence, and border security issues are only a few of the many others. Host-Hostage, taking in kidnapping, robbery, violence, insurgency, civil and political disturbance, and other horrific crimes are threatening Nigeria's security (Matazu (2013; Mejabi, 2012). Fights between Fulani herders and farmers have exploded in recent years, becoming out of control. The conflict between herders and their host communities for grazing pastures is a daily occurrence (Ekhomu, 2020).

Conflicts between religions are sometimes the consequence of misinterpretation or outright ignorance and intolerance against other faiths. Since the 1990s, Nigeria has been plagued by periodic religious and ethnic violence. Conflicts between Christians and Muslims, whether fundamentalists or moderate, have been implicated in a number of these tragedies. Religious or local civic leaders have often sparked these confrontations for political gain. There have been numerous ethnic and religious upheavals throughout the 2000s (Ekhomu, 2020) and the more recent Boko Haram insurgency and banditry. Natural disasters such as landslides, earthquakes, fires, floods and volcanic eruptions, the National Emergency Management Agency, military, Nigerian Security and Civil Defence Corps (NSCDC), Fire Service and Nigerian Police Force must work together to assist in evacuating endangered persons, controlling the crowd, protecting the public and private property, and delivering humanitarian assistance (Shiyabade, 2020).

Inter-agency collaboration is needed to deal with the threat of instability along the country's borders. The top security threats in this area are smuggling, piracy, alien influx, insurgency, commando raid/air bombardment, subversive penetration, and military incursion. According to this list, Nigeria's border security has, and might, be compromised in various ways (Imobighe, 2000). The security agencies, including the military, Customs Service, Immigration Service, Nigerian Police Force, DSS, and NIA, must work together to combat this insecurity. Political elites, political parties, and even governments have encouraged or acquiesced to importing, acquiring, distributing, and using small and light weapons (SALWs) during election seasons (Ikelegbe, 2014). Nigeria has been plagued by post-election violence on a number of occasions. For example, the 2011 election saw more post-election violence than in any of the years before it. Inter-agency rivalry persists in Nigeria despite the country's security concerns.

Gap in the Literature

The literature review on peace support and its success has progressed significantly over the years, as evidenced by the preceding literature. It is impossible to analyse the "value-added" of peace support in the second wave research since it focuses on cases in which peacekeepers were deployed rather than those in which no such intervention happened. Surveys of all conflicts' statistics have resolved this issue. Most importantly, it highlighted a shaky underpinning of the concept upon which peace support activities were built. For peace and assistance, it's important to know if peacekeepers tend to take on easier or more difficult instances. To put it another way, peacekeepers can't make much of a difference if they exclusively deploy to places where peace is a given. It is important to highlight that successful peacekeeping operations are more often when peacekeepers are deployed to more demanding environments. As a result of this study, it is hoped that Nigerian assistance for peace operations in Africa and Nigeria will be better contextualised, allowing for a clearer assessment of the costs and benefits and difficulties of such operations in Nigeria.

Theoretical Framework

This research is based on Fosdick's (1999) Organizational Theory. The research will look at transaction cost economics. This approach better explain both formal and informal methods of the Inter-agency Corporation.

Organizational Theory. Transaction Cost Economics is a fundamental part of the economic strategy since it examines the fundamental concerns of why organisations exist and how they manage their operations. When it comes to constructing and organising transactions, businesses are designed to do it orderly and predictable. Hierarchical coordination is more effective than market-based coordination. Therefore, it is possible to argue that organisational structures evolve as a result of cost savings on contract arrangement and implementation. An international relations theorist (Hasenclever, Meyer & Rittberger 1997; Hart 1995) has utilised this logic to explain international security arrangements and international regimes (Hasenclever, Meyer & Rittberger 1997; Hart 1995). "This would suggest that the development of coordination mechanisms in peace support operations should reflect the relative operating costs of alternative techniques for coordinating inter-organizational contacts," he said. It's reasonable to assume more hierarchical methods of coordination with clear directions and authority where transaction costs are high (Lipson, 2017). Another study looks at the interplay between economies of scale, governance costs, and the price of opportunism by David (1999). To control the extent to which the pyramid will exist in the security sector, he says that operational costs interact with threat levels. In this situation, the expectation is that States will cooperate as rational units. However, they are too narrow to accommodate the wide range of actors involved in complicated peace assistance operations (many of whom cannot be included in the small group of rational actors, such as NGOs and local actors).

Many interdependent actors participate in the mission's accomplishment, so information exchange and coordination are critical to the mission's success. It was recommended that transaction costs approach. However, it is useful to highlight that the degree of the pyramid is a function of operation costs and must be treated cautiously. Inter-organizational cooperation can benefit more from informal networks of actors involved in peace support operations, which are better at informal coordination. The chain of command is less flexible than a network. Due to the fact that parties in a network are dependent on each other's measurements of their resources, it is possible to benefit by pooling resources (Naim 2013). As a result of these social, technological, and economic shifts, network-based coordination has grown more prominent in terms of its ability to simplify teamwork and innovation (Alter & Hage, 1993). As the number of information increases, Alter and Hage (1993) claim that this new governance machinery is increasingly replacing both hierarchies and markets, because networks are more flexible than hierarchies, it is better suited in circumstances where there is a need for trust, rapid responses, reciprocity and shared understandings, thus enhancing cooperation.

It has been suggested by Lipson (2017) that the majority of coordination and interdependence in complex peacekeeping occurs bilaterally rather than multilaterally (when organisational nodes are firmly joined with multiply links). It's common for non-governmental organisations and civil affairs units to work together when they need escort or supplies from the local population, respectively (Weiss 1998). In these situations, informal gatherings are more appropriate. In situations when the ideals of agreement, fairness, and non-use of force are unstable or inoperative, more hierarchical, formal systems can be harmful or dysfunctional. As a result, the locals are aware of one or more actors' involvement in the mission. To be clear, this is not to say that formal assemblies are not important for inter-organizational coordination of peace support operations, but rather that informal networks are more likely to be developed when the actors are involved in ongoing, complementary activities or in situations where operational integration is required, or under conditions of uncertainty. These informal networks often avoid formal assemblies that are ineffective. Peace support operations can benefit from their development when the formal assemblies create a hurdle or even a buffer in the way of the goal at hand.

To make up for formal arrangements' flaws, informal networks are often used in conjunction with them. This could lead to circumstances where the official structures of the organisation are just ceremonial in severe situations (Alexander, 1995). To meet political demands, organisations that decouple inter-organizational coordination from formal structures yet maintain hierarchical (informal) structures can benefit from this kind of decoupling (Brunsson, 1989).

2. METHODOLOGY

Research Design

Research design is a methodical process to answer questions objectively, accurately, and inexpensively. The research design of this study was cross-sectional survey design. This was considered appropriate for this study as the variables involved in the study was not manipulated but considered retrospectively in the way they occurred.

Population, Sample Size and Sampling Technique

A population is a group of people, cases, or objects that share a set of characteristics that are distinct from the rest of the population. In this case, the target population is three thousand (3,000) officers of the Nigerian Military, which includes two thousand (2,000) Nigerian Army officers, six hundred and fifty thousand (650) Nigerian Airforce officers, as well as three hundred and fifty (350) Nigerian Navy officers. Using purposive sampling allows a student to pick cases that are relevant to the goal and so provides an acceptable and sufficient sample size. As a result, the sample size is calculated statistically using the Krejcie and Morgan (1970) sample size formula and the sample size determination table to ensure that the computed sample size is in line with the intended sample size. The study used a sample of 88 participants, which was calculated as follows:

$$S = \frac{X^2 NP (1-P)}{D^2(N-1) + X^2 P(1-P)}$$

Where:

S = required sample size

x = z-value (e.g. 0.95 for 95% confidence level)

N = population size

P = population proportion (expressed in decimal, assumed to be 0.5 or 50%)

D = degree of accuracy (5%) expressed as a portion (0.5) of the margin error.

Substituting into the equation,

$$S = \frac{(0.95)^2 \times 3000 \times 0.5 (1-0.5)}{0.05^2 \times (3000-1) + 0.95^2 \times 0.5 (1-0.5)}$$

$$S = \frac{3.8416 (1500)(0.5)}{0.0025 (2999) + 3.8416 (0.5)(0.5)}$$

$$S = \frac{676.875}{7.4975 + 0.9604}$$

$$S = \frac{676.875}{7.72} = 88$$

Probability sampling was used in this study to select a small number of participants from the entire population. There are two types of probability sampling: unrestricted (such as with simple random sampling) and restricted (such as with complicated probability sampling). Respondents from each of Nigeria's armed forces were recruited through stratified random sampling. In order to compare groups, stratified random sampling ensures that all groups are appropriately sampled. The list of military personnel serves as the sampling frame's stratum. There are two ways to stratify data: proportionately or disproportionately based on the number of strata in the data set. For this reason, a proportionate sample was used in the study to choose participants from each of the strata.

Method of Data Collection

The primary and secondary sources of data collecting were used in this research work, respectively. Data is gathered mostly through interviews, observations, questionnaires and surveys, as well as discussions in focus groups. A combination of in-depth interviews and questionnaires is used in this research work. Researchers interview one or more individuals and document their responses to open-ended questions when conducting qualitative research. In order to obtain the participants for the interview, this study uses the snowball method. It's a non-probability or chain-referral sampling strategy in which the samples contain characteristics that are hard to come by. Referrals from current subjects are used as a sampling approach to enlist the next participant to be interviewed for the study. This means that one person will decide the next individual to be interviewed. It was decided to use these techniques to use participants' experiences and understandings of the research topics as evidence.

Method of Data Analysis

Data were analysed using Content Analysis Techniques and Quantitative Approaches. The collected data were coded and entered into a computer to generate descriptive statistics. Additionally, the researcher performed a thematic analysis on a collection of texts, such as interview transcripts, to look for recurring themes, such as ideas and patterns of meaning. Charts, graphs, and tables were used to present the data for additional debate and analysis. Regression analysis was utilised to determine if there is a connection between inter-agency collaboration and peace support activities among Nigerian military personnel in order to improve the analysis by citing high points of certain valid views and other connected assertions.

Validity and Reliability of the Instrument

As part of an effort to demonstrate internal consistency, researchers use the instrumentation validation procedure to demonstrate to their audiences that the study's findings are in line with what the umpires concluded. Validity testing was carried out through the use of a pilot study technique. When it comes to the reliability of a test, it's all about finding out how consistent, trustworthy, predictable and accurate the results are for the same participants at different times or under different conditions.

Ethical Considerations

Participation in the event is entirely up to each individual. In addition, participants can be assured that their personal information, including their names and ranks, will stay private. Questions about the participants' names and ranks will not be included because participants will explain that they are fully anonymous.

3. RESULTS

Data Presentation

The data presentation comprises a description of the dataset disseminated for the research with the primary variables included, the classifications and breakdowns utilised, the reference area, and a summary of the period covered. The study makes use of these kinds of descriptive statistics. Coded field survey information is presented in this part, along with descriptive statistics.

Descriptive Statistics

Table 1 comprises the demographic information for this study's participants, which was used to compile the descriptive statistics. One hundred percent of the 88 participants completed the survey. twenty-five women and fifty men took part in the study, with a further thirteen people declining to answer the question about their gender. Only surveys that were completed from beginning to end were considered for data analysis, therefore a total of 70 participants in the survey, with 15 women (21.4% of the total) and 55 men (78.6% of the total).

Table 1: Years of Service by Gender and Status Description of Nigerian Military Personnel

Variable	Married (n=14)	Single (n=56)	Total
Gender			
Male	10(14.3)	45(64.3)	55(78.6)
Female	4(5.7)	11(15.7)	15(21.4)
Years of Service			
<5	3(4.3)	18(25.7)	21(30)
5 – 9 ^β	7(10.0)	30(42.9)	37(53)
10 – 14	2(2.9)	8(11.4)	10(14)
≥ 15	2(2.9)	0(0.0)	2(3)
Mean ± SD	3.5 ± 2.1	14.0 ± 11.2	17.5 ± 31.1
Sample Size of Military Personnel		(70)	100%
Male		55	78.6%
Female		15	21.4%

Source: Researcher's Computation from Field Survey 2023

Table 1 shows that the male military personnel participated more during inter-agency cooperation and peace support operations as they represent 55(78.6%) of respondents while women are only 15(21.4%) of the respondents. It implies that male security operatives are preferred to female security operatives and have no basis for gender sensitivity. The Nigerian government does administer more men into the Nigerian Military forces because the male counterparts have physical fitness in strength and stamina. The table further shows that 45(64.3%) of the male respondents are single and have been in service for over eight years as it falls within the service year of 5 to 9 years, representing 30(42.9%) respondents. This is significant as the military personnel who have years of experience in warfare and peacekeeping will focus more on the mission since no family ties distraction, implying that the nation (Nigeria) is well represented during international peacekeeping operations. It further infers that they have the requisite experience and knowledge about peace-support procedures and, therefore, are competent and skilful to provide accurate and reliable information necessary for drawing a valid conclusion for the study. Further descriptive figures are presented in the figures below.

Question One: How has the Nigerian Armed Forces benefited by engaging in peace support operations through interagency cooperation?

Table 2: Perception of Nigerian Military Personnel on Interagency Cooperation

S/No	Items	Mean	%
1	I feel fulfilled that Nigeria has benefited from armed forces engagement in peace support operations through interagency cooperation	4.6	92
2	A great deal of fulfilment is derived from my role as I partner with other security operatives	2.8	56
3	I am personally involved in my missions during inter-agency cooperation	3.1	62
4	I enjoy talking about my mission with other security operatives on inter-agency cooperation	3.9	78
5	The most significant things that occur to me during any mission are related to my co-security operatives	2.3	46
6	I would be less fulfilled without my role as a co-security operative or significant other	3.8	76
7	I am often discouraged during security missions as I collaborate with other security operatives	4.2	84
8	My demands are so great they often take me away from my mission when collaborating with other security operatives	3.6	72

9	There is no synergy on the nature of the relationship among the various security agencies	4.1	82
10	Great fulfilment in my life comes from my role as an inter-agency cooperator with other security operatives	2.1	42
11	Generally speaking, I am satisfied with inter-agency cooperation during peacekeeping	3.4	68
12	I am satisfied and feel supported by other security operatives during inter-agency cooperation	2	40
13	Inter-Agency Cooperation is an effective tool of national and international diplomacy	2.2	44
14	There are some professional interests derived through Inter-Agency Cooperation	3.6	72

Source: Researcher's Computation from Field Survey 2023

The mean response in Table 2 S/No. 1 shows that Nigeria has many benefits by engaging the military personnel in peace support operations through inter-agency cooperation. The calculated mean falls within the accepted criteria above 2.5, which is 4.6 (92%). 'This implies that Nigeria has always sent her soldiers to PSOs despite the challenges and the economic costs facing Nigeria during peacekeeping operations. Nigeria is one of the highest five countries that provide troops to UN peacekeeping operations on a continuous basis. As previously mentioned, the Nigerian military has received worldwide recognition for its remarkable work in peacekeeping. It's worth noting that peacekeeping has evolved into a stand-in for on-the-job training by serving as a continuous procedure on the ground.

Soldering can become more realistic with the encounters that occur in the mission area. PSO deployments test Nigerian soldiers' expertise with modern high-tech weapons in a period where military technology is constantly being improved. Also, in PSOs, inter-agency training has been successfully completed. Thus, Nigerian soldiers are able to communicate with soldiers from other countries. These have allowed Nigerian soldiers to inter-relate with other nations' armed forces, thus encouraging learning and training on their tactics and organizational models of operations. Nigeria has also been using peacekeeping machinery to decode her inspiring quest for African leadership into certainty. Its contributions to PSOs have boosted the country's military and diplomatic status within the international system. Through the instrumentation of the peacekeeping force, Nigeria has assumed a prominent actor in global conflict management. Nigeria has shown a significant obligation to promoting global peace and security through her participation in PSOs. The country has particularly demonstrated its ability when conducting sub-regional PSOs missions.

Consequently, Nigeria has leveraged her peace support role as a basis to claim a seat in an extended UN Security Council. With a specific position to UN operations, Nigerian involvement in peacekeeping has been a likely source of revenue generation for Nigeria. This is so as the contributing nations to UN PSO are eligible for numerous repayments. These include refunds for equipment used in mission areas, clothing, food items, troops monthly allowances and individual equipment. Compensation on hardware has sometimes provided Nigeria funds to purchase new hardware to replace the obsolete ones. Although refunds are always delayed because of UN cash shortages, economic gains can still accrue to the country for her participation in a UN PSO if done correctly. Overall, the amount retained by the Nigerian government from UN troops allowance has therefore amounted to a significant income for the country. Thus, contrary to the widespread impression that Nigeria's involvement in PSO is a trench on the economy, the reality is that such involvement in the UN operations and missions can constitute a means for foreign exchange for Nigeria.

Question Two: What is the nature of the relationship among the various security agencies in peace support operations?

The mean response in Table 3 S/No. 1 shows no peaceful relationship among the various security agencies in peace support operations as the calculated mean falls within the accepted criteria of above 2.5, which is 3.7 (74%). 'This implies that even though the security agencies collaborate during peace support operations, there is usually friction amongst them due to one reason or the other. Security operatives, rather than exploring avenues for cooperation and collaboration in improving sharing intelligence, capacity building and security, sometimes involve insalubrious conflicts. Intra-agency conflicts, lack

of joint training, lack of professionalism and indiscipline contribute to such disputes. Sometimes, a particular security agency contends to take credit for some success during the joint operation. Although they independently and jointly played their corresponding legitimate roles, such conflict situations undoubtedly often have serious negative consequences for national security.

There are several causes of inter-agency conflicts within the security sector in Nigeria. These include duplicated and conflicting roles and responsibilities assigned to some of the security operatives in the Acts that established them. An example is the duplication of functions between the Nigeria Police and the NSCDC; also The Department of State Service (DSS) and National Intelligence agencies actively collaborated without adequate recognition; such feelings, whether real or perceived, can set a stage for uncooperative attitudes, particularly in intelligence sharing, to aid the successful conduct of an operation and this also create inadequate recognition of roles played by various security operatives during peace support operations such as the counter-insurgency and counter-terrorism operations within the nation. Indiscipline on the part of some security personnel sometimes causes inter-agency conflicts. The Security agencies uphold a high level of discipline, and efforts are made to ensure this flow across the Services. There have been instances in which personnel would refuse to pay compliments otherwise regarded as a salutation or the traditional military greetings, thus resulting in the acclaimed senior officer challenging the other. This situation sometimes results in conflicts that may lead to more severe Inter-Agency conflicts.

Question Three: What challenges are confronting the Nigerian Armed Forces personnel during peace support operations with other agencies?

Table 3: Perception of Nigerian Military Personnel on Peace Support Operations

S/No	Items	Mean	%
1	There is no peaceful relationship among the various security agencies in peace support operations	3.7	74
2	The challenges confronting the Nigerian Armed Forces personnel during peace support operations are as a result of Inter-Agency Cooperation	2.0	40
3	Participating in peace support operations has enabled me to appreciate the devastating effects of war	2.1	42
4	My roles in peacekeeping missions interfere with my co-security operatives' activities	4.3	86
5	Peace support operations send positive signals about Nigerian Military's ability to handle its internal security and external issues	3.6	72
6	There is tension about balancing all my responsibilities during peace support operations	2.4	48
7	I should change something about my roles during peace support operations to balance all my responsibilities	2.1	42
8	I have a high level of happiness and fulfilment with my co-security operatives during peace support operations	4.4	88
9	I have great satisfaction with the policies and programs provided by the Nigerian Government to promote peace support operations	2.2	44
10	I have great satisfaction with the quality of time spent with family after peace support operations	2.3	46
11	I have high-level of happiness with my family situation during peace support operations	2.4	48

12	I have great satisfaction with the quality of time spent on leisure activities	4.1	82
13	Participating in peace support operations has led to the building of economic and diplomatic ties with countries	2.3	46
14	There are political benefits to gained by participating in peace support operations	4.2	84

Source: Researcher's Computation from Field Survey 2023

The mean response in Table 3, S/No. 2 shows that the specific challenge of the Nigerian Army during peace support operations is not interagency cooperation as the calculated mean falls within the rejected criteria of below 2.5, which is 2.0 (40%). It establishes that interagency cooperation is not the main challenge of peace support operations. During the interview session, some of the challenges they faced were enumerated as follows.

The Absence of a Peace Support Operations Policy. The Nigerian government sends contingents without properly articulated and focused goals because no vibrant national peace support operation policy exists. This has resulted in losing resources and personnel, restoring peace, and withdrawing for other nations to enjoy the fruit of their labour. In addition, there is no synergy between relevant ministries and agencies for carefully planned peacekeeping operations to achieve set objectives. In the absence of such a policy, strategic planning became a severe and recurrent problem. Nigeria contingent encountered a lot of issues in planning for PSO due to the lack of this policy.

Human Resources. Human resources challenges in the Nigerian Army have become noticeable in recent times. The inception of the Boko Haram insurgency in the country has resulted in most personnel being deployed to Internal Security operations. Military personnel have to be drawn from different units to form a battalion with the required strength to meet the United Nations standards for deployment to the mission area. Harmonisation of the Nigerian military units in manpower development would positively equip the Nigerian Army for effective participation in PSOs.

Logistics. In a continent such as Africa, where volatile situations arise overnight, distances are vast; infrastructure is often nonexistent or inoperable; it is glaringly apparent that any viable standby force must be able to deploy within hours throughout thousands of kilometres. This would probably best bring out the issues of Logistics and Sustainability of the Armed Forces to be deployed. Beyond the planning support, where the UN has an excellent track record, especially with the AU, there is the need to address logistics challenges. The lack of Contingent Own Equipment (COE) has been one of the major problems of African peacekeeping forces. The pattern of the logistical challenges faced by Nigerian soldiers deployed on PSOs has included lack of adequate medical facilities, lack of sufficient quantity vehicles, individual soldier kitting and insufficient communication equipment.

Language Barrier. Most conflict states are French-speaking states or English, Portuguese or Arabic, which posed a major problem to the Nigerian Army personnel in PSO. The Nigerian military had to get interpreters to communicate with the host nation and peacekeepers from non-English speaking countries. This same problem existed in the Darfur (UNAMID) and Mali (AFISMA) peacekeeping, though at a lower level as some Nigerian Army personnel understand and speak passable Arabic and French. Therefore, the need to encourage more of its personnel to learn Arabic, French, Spanish and Portuguese, to list a few.

Funding. Another primary challenge Nigeria faces regarding peacekeeping is inadequate military funding since it has an adverse impact on supporting ongoing and future peacekeeping operations. However, Nigeria is not the only nation in this group. Fiscal pressures on military funding are widespread throughout African countries. The African nation-states' delicate economies are ill-situated to man, train and equip their military and police forces to support the several peacekeeping missions. Consequently, these conditions contribute to the haphazardly screening and poorly trained personnel for critical out-of-area deployments supporting UN missions.

4. DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The analysed data has revealed that for the Nigerian military continued military support to other nations of the world during crises, peace support operations become eminent and achievable through inter-agency cooperation. Findings have shown that during peace support operations, only experience military personnel are deployed with requisite experience and knowledge about peace-support procedures; as such, each military personnel is expected to play his or her role effectively and efficiently.

The study found intrinsic and extrinsic motivations for participating in peace support operations. This study specifically found that the love of the job, the need to build peace, and participation allowances are the three essential motivations. It is worthy to note that motivation incentives play a significant role in the day-to-day performance of workers in every organization. Therefore, it is clear that military performance of any sort is a function of incentive obtained from the organization and thereby improves and increases productivity. Military motivation matters a lot and should be of concern for military high command. Therefore, getting the best out of personnel means that they should be well motivated. This proposition applies to the organization, which implies that the motivation of staff on whom the considerable responsibility of furthering organizational goals rests must take top priority if the organization continues to enjoy maximum performance from the teamwork. While traditional economic theory concentrates on monetary incentives as the primary motivator behind decision making, recent theoretical and experimental findings illustrate that non-monetary or intrinsic motivation significantly impact an agent's activities. Motivation guide people's actions and behaviours toward the achievement of some goals. Therefore, in working relationships and other contexts, motivation is often described as intrinsic or extrinsic. Intrinsic motivation, deriving from the person or the activity itself, positively affects behaviour, performance, and wellbeing. An essentially motivated individual will be committed to his work to the extent to which the job inherently contains rewarding tasks.

This study equally found that participating in peace support operations has been beneficial to the respondents concerning work and family-related effects. Participating in peace support operations since the respondents have acquired new knowledge and skills, making them better military personnel in combat. This knowledge acquisition stems from the fact that Nigeria is a developing country with a limited budget that cannot be invested in state-of-the-art military equipment. However, through the participation of peace support operations, Nigerian military personnel are trained on the latest and current military manoeuvres and practices. In effect, peace support operations provide the perfect opportunity for Nigerian military personnel to be introduced to new equipment and training methods.

It was found that participating in peace support operations comes with financial and monetary rewards. The findings are not surprising considering the difficult economic situation in Nigeria, which necessitates soldiers being pushed to look for avenues of augmenting their meager income. This finding also points to the fact that cash or monetary incentive is a significant motivator for employees, be it soldiers or those found in corporate entities. This study found that soldiers encounter several challenges during peace support operations. The main challenges included overlaps and role ambiguities that tend to affect soldiers' performance, limited capacity and resource constraints that sometimes affect their ability to deliver, especially in protecting civilians and enforcing peace. It is also found that the soldiers encounter stress-related issues and challenges such as combat stress conflicts between meeting their family's needs and meeting work demands. Research has suggested that families can be negatively affected by Post-Traumatic Stress Disorder (PTSD) symptoms such as insomnia, recurring dreams, avoidance, intrusive thoughts, depression, and flashbacks. This study suggests that transitioning back to family life incurs demanding changes for the husbands or wives, as the case may be.

The United Nations is not an organization but a network of international organizations, agencies, programs, and funds. This system was created to achieve the goals outlined in Article 1 of the UN Charter, including maintaining international peace and security. Over the years, peacekeeping has evolved from a primarily military model of observing cease-fires and separation of forces to incorporate a complex model of military, police and civilians working together to help lay the foundations for sustainable peace. This complex system is addressed as multidimensional peacekeeping. It deals with issues ranging from security sector reform, to capacity building of the state's authority, from community development to disarmament of combatants, from electoral assistance to human rights. This variety of activities involves different units at their turn supported by a logistic and administrative apparatus. They work in various PSO missions, each headed by a UN Secretary-General representative. Even though Nigeria being the top troop contributors, assert that their behaviour toward UN peacekeeping is solely for the benefit of the international society, it cannot be denied that the pursuit of their interests heavily drives their actions. It is explained that all nations are tempted, and few have been able to resist the temptation for long to clothe their particular aspirations and activities in the moral purposes of the universe. States will always be conflicted because prioritising their aims and objectives will always be in their favour.

Nigeria might have realised that UN peacekeeping is an effective way to fulfil its responsibilities to itself and the world, hence its track record in contributing troops, serving the needs of other nations by contributing troops for UN peace missions. Nigeria can equally pursue their interests, but important to respect other nations interests while protecting and promoting one's interests. Nigeria tries to maintain its status in UN peacekeeping as it is highly beneficial. Nigeria can equally pursue its national interests while enjoying a favourable reputation as a peacekeeper.

Based on the qualitative study findings, when peace support operations are effectively managed can lead to a win-win status quo for all stakeholders: the state, the soldiers, and the host nation. For this study to be justified, a correlation analysis was carried out on the perception of the military on inter-agency cooperation and peace support operations to test if they are related; the result showed that they are strongly statistically significant $r = 0.936$, $p < 0.05$, which indicates that peace support operation has a close relationship with inter-agency cooperation where the experienced and expertise of individuals collaboration, the more satisfied they are with their missions.

5. CONCLUSION

In sum, the human security perspective suggests that a new set of peacekeeping strategies for intrastate conflicts should fulfil transition assistance functions, thus allowing the operator to provide a link between long-term expansion aids and alternative humanitarian assistance. The human security perspective also reminds us that upon undertaking such transition assistance functions, UN peacekeepers must seek to assist, not dictate, the transition process by respecting local initiatives, utilizing local resources, and nurturing the local capacity to develop a sense of ownership among local participants in the peacebuilding process. At the same time, the concept of peace-building can serve as a helpful analytical tool to envisage a linkage among the many tasks (such as nation-building, reconstruction, rehabilitation, governance, and empowerment) required in the transition process and establish a comprehensive view of the post-conflict strategies.

Specifically, this study concludes that benefits such as heightened image and reputation, largesse (economic and military equipment) from developing partners, and international diplomacy accrues to states like Nigeria. From an individualistic perspective, this study concludes that soldiers, especially those from developing countries such as Nigeria, stand to benefit from participating in peace support operations. Indeed, by participating in peace support operations, soldiers can gain economically financially and the opportunity to learn from the experiences of other nations.

6. RECOMMENDATIONS

Having examined Nigerian military personnel perception of inter-agency cooperation and peace support operations, from the findings of this study, it is recommended that all stakeholders, especially the UN and participatory countries, be aware that the soldiers are the peacekeepers and assist war-torn countries to recover from wars and conflicts. Therefore, soldiers on peace support operations must be well taken care of by providing proper military equipment, training, and, more importantly, meeting both the intrinsic and extrinsic needs of soldiers. The specific recommendations are as follows:

- i. The Nigerian Army should standardise its manpower generation process for units' preparation deployment to PSOs regarding the manpower challenges. This could be achieved if all postings for deployment are accomplished at least six months before a scheduled deployment. This would also lay the foundation for building unit cohesion and esprit de corps, qualities necessary for high-performing units.
- ii. In future participation of the Nigerian military in peace support operations, the mandate and achievable objectives should be spelt out for the safety and security of the Nigerian military personnel.
- iii. The Nigerian government and military should review and make the necessary adjustments to address all shortcomings that have already been identified in the administrative and logistical support to units deployed to PSOs.
- iv. The government should also set up a coordinating body for Nigerian peace support operations efforts within mission countries. The national coordinating body should help merge some Nigerian initiatives to be engaged in reconstruction works.
- v. The selection process for the peacekeeping mission should be done based on merit and competence to ensure an optimum result as more priority be considered for the welfare of its citizens and infrastructural development instead of its total devotion to peace support operations.

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